

Synthesis in the Pyrazolone Series. Action of Thiosemicarbazide and Semicarbazide on Ketonic Esters.

Part I.

BY

SATISH CHANDRA DE.

The behaviour of hydrazine hydrate towards β -ketonic esters was first investigated by Curtius and Jay (*J. pr. Chem.*, 39, 153) who obtained pyrazolone derivatives of the following type.

Rothenburg then published a series of papers in which he studied the action of hydrazine hydrate on various β -ketonic esters and β -diketones (*J. pr. Chem.*, 52, 23, 45; 51, 43, 140, 157; etc.). The action of phenylhydrazine and its substitution products on the ketonic esters has long been investigated by a host of investigators who obtained in this way a large number of pyrazolone derivatives.

The present work, a preliminary account of which will be reported here, was undertaken with a view to examine the type of compounds produced by the action of thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide on the various β -ketonic esters; and, as might be expected, owing to the

close resemblance in structure between hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide, the final condensation products of thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide with acetoacetic ester are quite analogous to those derived from hydrazine and phenylhydrazine.

The carbazides combine readily with acetoacetic ester to give the corresponding semi- and thiosemi-carbazones which part with alcohol on treatment with strong aqueous or alcoholic ammonia in the cold with the formation of pyrazolone derivatives.

It now requires to be proved whether the acetoacetic ester molecule reacts in its ketonic or enolic form. From the results of his investigation of acetoacetic ester phenylhydrazone Nef (*Annalen*, 266, 70) came to the conclusion that the resulting compound was not a hydrazone but a hydrazo-compound since by oxidation he was able to isolate an azo-compound from it. The present author has, however, ascribed the hydrazone formulæ to his semi- and thiosemi-carbazones as they could not be oxidised to azo-compounds. Consequently the acetoacetic ester has reacted like a ketone towards semi- and thiosemi-carbazides.

It is a remarkable fact that although the behaviour of both the semicarbazones towards cold ammonia is the same it differs greatly towards heat; for when heated either alone or in presence of water or alcohol the acetoacetic ester semicarbazone gives methylpyrazolone with the elimination of alcohol, ammonia and carbon dioxide whilst the corresponding thiosemicarbazone of acetoacetic ester gives, by such treatment, a derivative of

methylpyrazolone by the elimination of alcohol only. The 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide (II) is stable only in the cold as it splits off the carbamido group with great ease with the formation of 3-methylpyrazolone. The 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide is on the contrary a relatively stable substance which parts with the thiocarbamido group only on prolonged heating.

Both the semicarbazones of acetoacetic ester can react in dilute sodium carbonate solution with another molecule of acetoacetic ester. In this reaction a molecule of water, and a molecule of alcohol are eliminated and the product has formula (III).

The same product is formed by the action of acetoacetic ester on 3-methylpyrazolone-1-(thio)carbamide. The pyrazolones so obtained give all the reactions as enumerated by Rothenburg. With ferric chloride the pyrazolones give interesting colour reactions which will be described in the proper place.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Thiosemicarbazide with Acetoacetic Ester.

(a). *Acetoacetic Ester Thiosemicarbazone.*—When an aqueous solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (one mol.) was shaken up with acetoacetic ester (one mol.) the thiosemicarbazone separated out after some time (Freund and Schander, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2605); but the reaction takes place much more rapidly with the complete

separation of the thiosemicarbazone on allowing the mixture to react in presence of sodium acetate. The white precipitate so obtained was filtered from the mother-liquor, washed with water and crystallised from benzene. (Found: N = 20.96. $C_7H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N = 20.69 per cent.). With ferric chloride this substance gives no colour reaction. It reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate solution with the evolution of a gas.

(b). *3-Methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide*.—The thiosemicarbazone of acetoacetic ester was covered with strong ammonia and thoroughly stirred when the carbazone gradually went into solution with the evolution of heat; and after some time a small quantity of white needles of the ammonium salt of 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide separated out. This ammonium salt is very unstable as it liberates ammonia even at the ordinary temperature. By the careful addition of acid to the ammoniacal filtrate, the free base could be easily obtained as a voluminous precipitate of white needle-shaped crystals. It was also obtained as white needles by boiling the aqueous solution of its ammonium salt for some time. Crystallised from water it melts at 180° . (Found: N = 27.01. $C_5H_7ON_3S$ requires N = 26.75 per cent.).

The same compound was obtained when the acetoacetic ester thiosemicarbazone was boiled with water for some length of time. Unlike the corresponding 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide (to be described later) it is very stable and under ordinary conditions does not part with the thiocarbamido group. But by prolonged boiling with water or better by heating with concentrated aqueous or alcoholic potash it splits off the thiocarbamido group and is converted into 3-methylpyrazolone melting at 214° — 216° (*J. pr. Chem.*, 39, 52). (Found: N = 28.78. $C_4H_4ON_2$ requires N = 28.57 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in alcohol and difficultly so in water and can be conveniently crystallised from water containing a few drops of alcohol. With ferric chloride it gives a deep purple colour.

(c). *3-Methylisopyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide Hydrochloride* was obtained by treating 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide with conc hydrochloric acid and evaporating the solution to dryness on the water-bath. The residue was washed with absolute alcohol and then with ether. The hydrochloride so obtained is very hygroscopic and melts at 151° (not sharp). (Found: Cl=18.77. $C_5H_7ON_3S$, HCl requires Cl=18.35 per cent.).

(d). *4:4-Dibromo-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide*.— This compound was obtained by the action of excess of bromine in acetic acid solution on 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide suspended in the same solvent. The pyrazolone gradually dissolved forming a red solution. From acetic acid, in which the dibromo-compound is soluble, a yellowish brown crystalline mass was obtained after neutralisation with sodium carbonate. It is insoluble in the other ordinary organic solvents and was, therefore, purified by dissolving in acetic acid and precipitating with alkali. It melts at 250° . (Found: Br=50.99. $C_5H_6ON_3SBr_2$ requires Br=50.79 per cent.).

(e). *4-Bromo-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide*.— The pyrazolone (b) was suspended in acetic acid and bromine (two atoms) dissolved in the same solvent was gradually added. The pyrazolone first dissolved in the acid with the evolution of heat and shortly after the monobromo-derivative separated out in the form of a yellow crystalline mass, which was filtered, washed and finally crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow crystals melting at 220° . (Found: Br=34.18; N=18.16. $C_5H_6ON_3SBr$ requires Br=33.90; N=17.80 per cent.).

(f). *4-Benzene-azo-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide* was obtained by gradually adding the equivalent quantity of diazotised aniline to the pyrazolone (b) suspended in acetic acid and cooled in ice. The reaction began at once with the evolution of heat and formation of a red solution. The mixture was thoroughly stirred during all the time the diazo-solution was added and then allowed to stand for some time to bring the reaction to completion. The red crystalline solid that separated out was filtered off, washed with water and purified by crystallisation from water when it was obtained in orange crystals melting at 217° with decomposition. (Found: $N=27.07$. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_5S$ requires $N=26.82$ per cent.).

(g). *4-iso Nitroso-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide* was obtained either by passing gaseous nitrous acid through the pyrazolone (b) suspended in acetic acid or by adding sodium nitrite solution. The reaction began with the separation of a light yellow crystalline mass. This was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from water in yellow needles melting at 180° . (Found: $N=30.39$. $C_5H_6O_2N_4S$ requires $N=30.11$ per cent.).

The *isonitroso* compound has a strong acid reaction. It is soluble in alkalis and from the alkaline solution it can be precipitated by acids. It gives Liebermann's *isonitroso* reaction. The aqueous solution gives with silver nitrate solution an insoluble silver salt of yellow colour.

(h). *3-Methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbonyl- β -amidocrotonic ester*¹ was obtained when acetoacetic ester (two mols.) and thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (one mol.) were shaken up with excess of sodium carbonate solution.

¹ For the sake of convenience the acetoacetic ester has been supposed to react on the urea group of the hydrazone or of the pyrazolone in enolic form (compare Behrend, *Annalen*, 229, 5).

The liquid was filtered from a small quantity of the undissolved hydrazone and the filtrate on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a white precipitate of 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbonyl- β -amidocrotonic ester. The same compound was obtained when the freshly prepared thiosemicarbazone of acetoacetic ester was shaken with excess of acetoacetic ester in presence of a sufficient quantity of dilute sodium carbonate solution. Thus treated the thiosemicarbazone gradually went into solution; the clear solution was allowed to stand for some time and then acidified when a white precipitate was obtained. It was purified by crystallisation from a mixture of alcohol and water when it was obtained in white needles melting at 145° . (Found: N=15.82. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3N_3S$ requires N=15.61 per cent.).

It is almost insoluble in cold water and alcohol but dissolves readily in hot alcohol. With ferric chloride it gives a beautiful deep indigo-blue coloration. It is very stable towards heat in presence of ordinary solvents but on prolonged boiling with water or alcohol it decomposes into acetoacetic ester and 3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide. A solution of the substance gives with silver nitrate an insoluble silver salt.

CONDENSATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE WITH ACETO-ACETIC ESTER.

(a). *Acetoacetic Ester Semicarbazone*.—The method of preparation of this compound is the same as that for the corresponding thiosemicarbazone of acetoacetic ester. A mixture of acetoacetic ester (one mol.), semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous solution (one mol.) and sodium acetate was shaken. After some time the semicarbazone separated out in the form of a white amorphous powder; this was filtered, washed with water

and then crystallised from ether. (Found: $N = 22.62$. $C_7H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires $N = 22.46$ per cent.).

The semicarbazone of acetoacetic ester crystallises from ether in beautiful white needles melting at 129° . It is easily soluble in hot water and alcohol. It gives no colour reaction with ferric chloride. It reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate solution with the evolution of a gas; mercuric oxide is also reduced by the boiling aqueous solution of the hydrazone. When this semicarbazone was heated at 115° — 120° it evolved ammonia gas and at the same time turned brown. The temperature was maintained at 120° — 125° for several hours till no more ammonia gas was evolved. The residue was then extracted with hot water, boiled with charcoal and from the filtrate a white crystalline substance was obtained melting at 214 — 16° , which is identical with 3-methylpyrazolone of Curtius (*loc. cit.*). The same compound was also obtained when the semicarbazone was boiled with water.

(b). *3-Methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide*.—For the preparation of this compound the above semicarbazone was shaken with ammonia solution and allowed to stand for some time after which the liquid was filtered from any undissolved semicarbazone. From the filtrate the pyrazolone was precipitated by acid as a white crystalline mass. This was dissolved for purification in the least quantity of methyl alcohol and precipitated by ether. It melts at 192° . (Found: $N = 30.12$. $C_5H_7O_2N_3$ requires $N = 29.79$ per cent.).

It is moderately soluble in cold water and alcohol and insoluble in ether. With ferric chloride it gives a blue coloration. By gentle warming of its aqueous or alcoholic solution it easily parts with the carbamido group and forms 3-methylpyrazolone.

(c). *3-Methylisopyrazolone Hydrochloride*.—3-Methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide combines very easily with acids and bases to form unstable salts. When treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution evaporated to dryness, a residue was obtained which was extracted with absolute alcohol. From the alcoholic solution a light yellow coloured oil separated out by the addition of ether. This oil was separated and allowed to stand in vacuum over sulphuric acid when it solidified to a crystalline mass of *3-methylisopyrazolone hydrochloride*. It is extremely hygroscopic. (Found: N=23.97; Cl=20.31. $C_5H_7O_2N_3$, HCl requires N=23.66; Cl=20.0 per cent.).

The ammonium salt of 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide could not be obtained in the solid state. By evaporation of its ammoniacal solution in vacuum over sulphuric acid the free base was obtained. The salt is stable in solution and its aqueous solution gave with silver nitrate a white precipitate of the silver salt, which is much more stable than 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide itself, but when long boiled with water it liberated the carbamido group and passed into the silver salt of 3-methylpyrazolone. (Found: Ag=53.32 $C_4H_5ON_2Ag$ requires Ag=52.68 per cent.).

(d). *4:4-Dibromo-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide* was obtained by treating the pyrazolone (b) dissolved in methyl alcohol with a slight excess of bromine in acetic acid solution. The reaction began with the evolution of heat. From the acid solution the dibromo-compound was obtained by neutralisation with alkali. It is insoluble in most organic solvents and was therefore purified by dissolving in acetic acid and precipitating with alkali. It melts at 225°. (Found: Br=53.74. $C_5H_5O_2N_3Br_2$ requires Br=53.51 per cent.). When the dibromo-

derivative was long boiled with water, it was converted into another substance melting at 184° and was found to be identical with the dibromo-3-methylpyrazolone of Rothenburg (*J. pr. Chem.*, 52, 37). (Found: $\text{Br}=62.74$. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{ON}_2\text{Br}_2$ requires $\text{Br}=62.50$ per cent.)

(e). *4-Benzene-azo-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide* was obtained in the form of a reddish brown crystalline mass by adding the calculated quantity of diazotised aniline to the methyl alcoholic solution of the pyrazolone (b). This was filtered off, washed and crystallised from alcohol. It melts at 235° . (Found: $\text{N}=28.86$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires $\text{N}=28.57$ per cent.). On long continued boiling it suffers decomposition and forms 4-benzene-azo-3-methylpyrazolone melting at $195-97^{\circ}$.

(f). *4-isoNitroso-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide* was obtained by passing gaseous nitrous acid through the methyl alcoholic solution of the pyrazolone. The solution was first coloured red and a yellow crystalline precipitate was formed which was filtered off, washed first with water and then with hot alcohol to free it from any unchanged starting material. It melts at 210° and is sufficiently pure for analysis. (Found: $\text{N}=33.32$. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires $\text{N}=32.94$ per cent.).

It is insoluble in organic solvents but on long boiling with water it gradually dissolves. The aqueous solution on cooling deposits crystals of 4-isonitroso-3-methylpyrazolone of Curtius and Rothenburg and is evidently formed by the elimination of the carbamido group from the above 4-isonitroso compound. The isonitroso-compound has a strong acid reaction and dissolves readily in alkalis from whose solution it can be precipitated by acids. An ammoniacal solution of the substance gives with silver nitrate a yellow precipitate of the isonitroso-silver salt.

(g). *3-Methylpyrazolone-1-carbonyl-β-amidocrotonic ester* was obtained by a method analogous to that described for the corresponding thiocarbonyl compound either from acetoacetic ester (two mols.) and semicarbazide hydrochloride (one mol.) or from acetoacetic ester semicarbazone and the ester in presence of dilute sodium carbonate solution, the substance being precipitated from the carbonate solution by dilute hydrochloric acid. For purification it was dissolved in cold sodium carbonate solution and re-precipitated by acid in white needles melting at 175.6° with decomposition. (Found: N = 16.91. $C_{11}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N = 16.60 per cent.).

It is insoluble in cold benzene, water and alcohol. It gives a deep blue coloration with ferric chloride. It is very unstable towards heat. When boiled with water it gradually dissolves with the evolution of ammonia and liberation of an oil floating on the water which was identified as acetoacetic ester and from the clear solution crystals of 3-methylpyrazolone were obtained. A methyl alcoholic solution of the substance gives with silver nitrate a silver salt in light yellow gelatinous form.

Further work on this line is in progress and will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

I avail myself of this opportunity of expressing my gratitude to Dr. J. C. Ghosh and Dr. P. C. Guha for the kind interest they have taken in this investigation.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY
DACCA.

Received, October 13, 1925.
